

JustREACH

D7.2- CDE Plan

WP7–Communication, dissemination and exploitation

15/02/2026

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EC Summary Requirements

1. Changes with respect to the DoA

No changes with respect to the work described in the DoA.

2. Dissemination and uptake

This deliverable serves as a reference document for consortium partners to plan, coordinate and implement all JustREACH's Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation (CDE) activities. All consortium partners contribute actively to the implementation of communication and dissemination actions through their networks at local, regional, national and European levels. The document also provides external stakeholders with a clear overview of the project's CDE approach, the main channels and activities planned, and how project results will be shared and exploited.

3. Short summary of results (<250 words)

This deliverable presents the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation (CDE) Plan of the JustREACH project. It outlines the strategic approach guiding all CDE activities, with the aim of ensuring visibility, uptake and long-term use of project results by relevant stakeholders. The document describes the main communication and dissemination tools and activities, including the project website, social media, newsletters, workshops, co-creation events, social learning videos, policy briefs, webinars and scientific publications. It also sets out how dissemination is supported through pilot regions, European platforms and synergies with related initiatives. The CDE plan also includes the key performance indicators (KPIs) to monitor progress and impact and is designed as a living document that will be updated on an annual basis to incorporate results and lessons learned.

4. Evidence of accomplishment

This report.

Preface

Across Europe, local and regional authorities are under growing pressure to respond to the accelerating impacts of climate change while maintaining economic growth and social cohesion. Many face limited resources, complex policy requirements and the challenge of ensuring that adaptation measures are both effective and fair. The aim of JustREACH is to advance just climate resilience by enhancing the capacity of authorities, businesses and citizens to design and implement adaptation actions that align with regional innovation and development strategies. Through co-creation, knowledge integration and practical application, the project supports a more equitable and resilient transition for all regions. The partners involved in JustREACH are:

TUD – DELFT UNIVESRITY OF TECHNOLOGY	NL	
BME – BUDAPEST UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY AND ECONOMICS	HU	
THNK – TH!NK-E	BE	
JR – JOANNEUM RESEARCH	AT	
DAEM – DIMOS ATHINAION EPICHEIRISI MICHANOGRAFISIS	GR	
QUB – QUEENS UNIVERSITY BELFAST	UK	
WIP – WIRTSCHAFT AND INFRASTUKTUR GMBH & CO. PLANUNGS KG	DE	
REGEA – NORTH-WEST CROATIA REGIONAL ENERGY AND CLIMATE AGENCY	HR	
LCF – BODENSEE-STIFTUNG	DE	
I-ENER – I-ENER	FR	
PBL – MINISTERIE VAN INFRASTUCUTUUR EN WATERSTAAT	NL	
HOL – HOLISTIC IKE	GR	
LUH – LEIBNIZ UNIVERSITEIT HANNOVER (L3S FORHUNGSZENTRUM)	DE	
UB – UNIVERSITY OF BERN	CH	

Executive Summary

This document defines the strategy that will guide the dissemination and communication activities of the JustREACH project throughout its duration. As a core output of Work Package 7, it provides the consortium members with a practical and coordinated framework to support the visibility, dissemination and uptake of project outputs.

The CDE strategy is built around three interconnected and mutually reinforcing pillars. Communication activities raise awareness of JustREACH and its focus on just climate resilience, adaptation implementation and regional development. Dissemination activities ensure that project results, tools and lessons learned reach relevant target audiences, including local and regional authorities, policymakers, practitioners, researchers and networks, through targeted and participatory activities. Finally, the exploitation strategy focuses on the longer-term use, and further development of project outputs, in collaboration with partner networks, pilot regions and European platforms.

The plan emphasises continuous engagement, co-creation with pilot regions and alignment with the EU Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change, with the aim of bridging the gap between adaptation research and action. It is conceived as a living document that will be reviewed and updated on an annual basis to reflect emerging results, stakeholders' feedback and evolving policy contexts.

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1 Introduction

Across Europe, local and regional authorities are under growing pressure to respond to the accelerating impacts of climate change and develop climate adaptation plans, in line with the [EU Climate Law](#) and [the EU Strategy on Adaptation to Climate Change](#). At the same time, these authorities are also expected to design and implement regional innovation strategies, including smart specialisation strategies, in order to access European funding and support regional development. While these policy agendas are closely interlinked in practice, authorities often face difficulties in aligning them during both planning and implementation. Limited administrative capacity, fragmented information across multiple platforms and the risk of unintended social and economic consequences make it challenging to move from design to effective implementation, particularly in regions with fewer resources.

JustREACH aims to support local and regional authorities in addressing these challenges by strengthening their ability to implement climate adaptation measures that are effective, socially fair and aligned with regional development priorities. The project focuses on practical needs that authorities face during implementation, such as understanding the social and economic implications of adaptation choices, identifying where adaptation can reinforce regional innovation and development goals, and avoiding missed opportunities and negative consequences for those who are most vulnerable to changes. To respond to these needs, JustREACH develops and tests a set of practical frameworks, assessment methods, decision-support tools and learning resources that can be used by authorities and practitioners in real planning and implementation contexts. These outputs are designed to be applicable across different territorial settings and to support informed decision-making rather than prescribe fixed solutions.

JustREACH is part of the wider EU Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change ecosystem and contributes to its objectives through a strong focus on implementation and capacity building. The project works closely with five pilot regions across different European climate adaptation regions. These are Lake Constance in Germany, Athens in Greece, Belfast in the United Kingdom, Zagreb in Croatia and Nouvelle-Aquitaine in France, covering a diverse range of adaptation challenges in urban, industrial and rural settings. Experience from the pilot sites is used to refine the project's outputs and to generate lessons that are relevant for other regions facing similar challenges. JustREACH also connects its results to existing European knowledge platforms and Mission communities, supporting the uptake of its tools and approaches by Mission signatories and other local and regional authorities seeking to translate adaptation plans into concrete action that strengthens just climate resilience.

1.1 Objectives of the CDE Strategy

The objective of the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation (CDE) strategy is to ensure that the results of JustREACH are visible, understood, used and taken forward by the actors who can apply them in practice. In line with Horizon Europe guidance,¹ **communication** refers to activities that raise

¹ European Commission: European Research Executive Agency, *Disseminating and exploiting results – A starter kit for EU-funded research and innovation projects*, Publications Office of the European Union, 2025, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2848/1949672>

awareness and understanding of the project and its purpose among a broad audience, **dissemination** focuses on the targeted transfer of knowledge and results to relevant stakeholders who can potentially make direct use of them, and **exploitation** concerns the uptake, reuse and further development of project outputs beyond the project's lifetime. These three pillars are complementary and mutually reinforcing and are addressed through a coordinated strategy throughout the duration of the project.

Through its CDE strategy, JustREACH supports the objectives of the EU Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change by focusing on implementation and capacity building rather than stand-alone knowledge production.

- **Communication activities** aim to position JustREACH within the broader Mission ecosystem, build trust with local and regional authorities and raise awareness of the links between climate adaptation, social justice and regional development.
- **Dissemination activities** are designed to facilitate the uptake of project results by practitioners, policymakers and Mission signatories through targeted engagement, peer learning and exchange across regions.
- **Exploitation activities** ensure that the tools, frameworks, learning materials and decision-support resources developed by the project remain accessible, usable and relevant beyond the project duration.

The CDE strategy supports the core activities and outputs defined in the Grant Agreement. These include co-design workshops with five pilot regions across different European climate adaptation regions to test tools and approaches and identify implementation barriers; a Transformation Bootcamp that builds the capacity of local and regional authorities and generates learning resources for wider reuse; the co-creation of social learning videos with pilot sites to demonstrate how adaptation and transformation can take place in practice; and the integration of JustREACH datasets and tools into existing European adaptation and regional development knowledge platforms. All these outputs and activities together support the use, reuse and further development of JustREACH results by Mission signatories, neighboring regions and other relevant actors, and contribute to long-term impact and just climate resilience.

Following the introduction in Chapter 1, this deliverable outlines the overall Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation approach of JustREACH. Chapter 2 presents the project's target audiences, building on Deliverable D7.1 "Identifying Key Audiences" and situating them within the wider EU Mission on Adaptation ecosystem. Chapters 3 and 4 describe the communication and dissemination strategies respectively, detailing the objectives, key messages, tools, activities and monitoring indicators designed to support visibility, engagement and uptake of project results. Chapter 5 sets out the exploitation strategy, explaining how JustREACH outputs will be used, reused and further developed beyond the project's lifetime. Finally, Chapter 6 outlines the next steps for implementing, monitoring and refining the CDE strategy as the project progresses.

1.2 Scope and Principles

The Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation strategy of JustREACH is **mission-driven** and **user-oriented**, reflecting the objectives and communication principles of the EU Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change. All CDE activities are designed to support the Mission's **focus on implementation, learning and capacity building**, and to contribute to ongoing discussions and actions within the Mission ecosystem. Communication efforts aim to ensure consistency with Mission messaging and to position JustREACH as a complementary and enabling initiative rather than a stand-alone project. The strategy prioritises **relevance for end users**, particularly local and regional authorities and practitioners, and focuses on practical challenges and solutions that can support decision-making and implementation in real policy and planning contexts.

Co-creation and place-based relevance are central principles guiding the scope of the CDE strategy. Activities are grounded in the specific needs, institutional settings and administrative realities of the five pilot regions, recognising that adaptation challenges and governance structures differ across territories. In line with recent Joint Research Centre work on place-based transformations,² the strategy acknowledges that effective adaptation requires solutions that are sensitive to local socio-economic conditions, spatial characteristics and governance contexts, rather than uniform approaches applied across regions. The CDE strategy therefore avoids one-size-fits-all messages and instead tailors communication and dissemination formats to regional and local conditions.

Accessibility, inclusiveness and **multilingualism** underpin all communication and dissemination activities. JustREACH aims to make its output understandable and usable by a wide range of audiences, including policymakers, practitioners, researchers and citizens. **Non-technical language** is prioritised, and the use of AI-related or jargon terminology is avoided unless it is directly relevant and clearly explained. Visual materials, storytelling formats and social learning videos are used to support understanding and engagement beyond expert communities. When needed, materials are adapted to different languages and cultural contexts to ensure broad accessibility and to support uptake across regions.

The CDE strategy follows **open science principles**, as outlined in the proposal, with the aim of increasing transparency, collaboration and reuse of research outputs. JustREACH promotes early and open sharing of methods, results, publications, data and software, including through open-access publishing and suitable repositories, while respecting ethical, legal and data protection requirements. Workshops and dissemination events are designed to be open and inclusive, encouraging participation beyond the consortium and enabling feedback to inform project activities.

Last but not least, **gender equality and inclusion** are embedded across all CDE actions. Co-production and co-creation activities ensure fair representation, equal participation and accessibility, with explicit attention to women's perspectives. The consortium's gender-balanced and women-led structure supports these principles and reinforces the project's commitment to equity and justice in both process and outcomes.

Figure 1 below illustrates the key design principles guiding the JustREACH CDE strategy.

² European Commission, Joint Research Centre (2024). *Innovation for place-based transformations*. Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg. DOI: 10.2760/234679 (JRC135826).

Figure 1. Core Principles

1.3 Timeline

Communication, dissemination and exploitation activities in JustREACH are implemented as a continuous and adaptive process that evolves with the project and the availability of results. Activities are monitored through monthly meetings with all consortium members to allow regular reflection and adjustment of messages, channels and formats based on internal progress, feedback from pilot sites and stakeholders, and developments in the wider policy and knowledge landscape. The timeline itself is used as a management tool and is periodically reviewed against project progress.

Phase 0 - Preparation (M0–M4) covered the initial preparation of the CDE strategy. During this phase, target audiences and communication channels were refined at both pilot and European levels, cultural considerations were assessed, and the project’s visual identity and core communication templates such as the project’s poster and leaflets were developed. This work informed the deliverable D7.1 “Identifying Target Audiences”.

Phase 1 – Planning (M4–M7) corresponds to the current phase at the time of preparation of this CDE Plan and focuses on establishing the project’s visibility and initial outreach. The project website has been launched, initial social media activity and partner-led outreach has been carried out, and participation in EU Mission on Adaptation Communities of Practice began. These actions aimed to introduce JustREACH, build early awareness and establish a baseline audience for subsequent communication and dissemination activities, with a primary focus on pilot regions and core stakeholders group already identified at the beginning of the project.

Phase 2 – Implementation (M7–M48) represents the main implementation phase for communication and dissemination. During this phase, social learning videos, policy outreach and policy briefs, scientific publications, and conference presentations are progressively developed and disseminated. Workshops, co-creation events and participation in Mission Communities of Practice continue throughout this phase, supporting peer learning and exchange across regions. As results progress, dissemination activities increasingly extend beyond the pilot regions to reach secondary and tertiary audiences, supporting spill-over and transferability of project outcomes.

Phase 3 – Sustainability (from M36 onwards) prepares for post-project exploitation and long-term impact. During this phase, the use and impact of project outputs will be assessed, and targeted

exploitation actions will be defined to support continued use beyond the project's lifetime. This phase also includes the organisation of the Transformation Bootcamp and the combined online and offline final dissemination events. Dissemination activities implemented in earlier phases provide the basis for these exploitation actions and support continuity beyond the project's duration.

An indicative overview of the timing of key dissemination activities is provided in Table 1. The table refers only to dissemination activities. Key project outputs, including frameworks, tools and implementation pathways, are disseminated through multiple activities across the phases shown below. The timeline remains indicative and may be refined in future updates of the CDE Plan to reflect project progress and emerging needs.

Table 1. Indicative timeline of dissemination activities

Activity	M1-12	M13-30	M31-48
Workshops and co-creation events	●	●	●
Participation in Mission Communities of Practice	●	●	●
Social learning videos		●	●
Policy outreach and policy briefs		●	●
Scientific publications		●	●
Conference presentations and side events		●	●
Transformation Bootcamp			●
Final online and offline dissemination events			●

1.4 Communication and dissemination management structure

The implementation of CDE activities in JustREACH follows a coordinated and collaborative approach involving all consortium partners. HOLISTIC coordinates all relevant activities, ensures consistency with the project's CDE objectives, and supports alignment across work packages.

Content for dissemination activities is developed jointly by the partners responsible for the relevant outputs and activities, with pilot partners playing a central role in providing context, evidence and local perspectives. Draft materials are shared with the HOLISTIC for coordination and consistency checks before publication or dissemination through project channels and external platforms.

To ensure timely and effective dissemination, partners inform HOLISTIC in advance of planned events, publications or policy interactions, during the monthly meetings. This allows the preparation of supporting communication materials and coordinated promotion through the project website, social media, newsletters and partner networks. All partners also will help to enlarge the audience of the project through their networks and channels and ensure the quality of the activities implemented.

Dissemination activities are implemented in a flexible manner, allowing adjustments based on project progress, feedback from stakeholders and emerging opportunities at local, national and European levels.

2. Target Audience

The Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation strategy of JustREACH builds directly on report “Identifying Target Audiences”³, which provides the project’s audience mapping and serves as the reference framework for all engagement activities. This chapter summarises the key audience groups identified in the above mentioned report and explains how they relate to the objectives of the CDE strategy and the wider EU Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change ecosystem.

The process of identifying the target audience followed an ecosystem-based approach, as it recognised that just and effective climate adaptation depends on interactions between multiple actors operating at local, regional, national and European levels. Audiences are treated as part of a broader landscape of users, enablers and beneficiaries of JustREACH results. The mapping distinguishes between primary, secondary and tertiary audiences based on their proximity to the project’s outputs, their capacity to act on or amplify results, and their influence on adaptation and regional development processes. This approach aligns with the Mission on Adaptation’s emphasis on multi-level governance, peer learning and collaboration across regions and sectors.

2.1 Primary Target Audiences

Primary audiences are the actors most closely linked to the project results. Their engagement will ensure that project tools and results respond to real policy and operational needs. These are:

- **Local authorities** (municipalities, cities and metropolitan authorities), which are responsible for climate adaptation planning and implementation, with a particular focus on Mission on Adaptation signatories and members of Mission Communities of Practice as well as Covenant of Mayor signatories and regions and cities receiving Cohesion Fund and Just Transition Fund support;
- **Local and regional actors in the five pilot regions** (municipal departments, public agencies, local networks and communities);
- **National and regional public agencies**, which coordinate climate adaptation, innovation, cohesion and territorial development policies.

2.2 Secondary Target Audiences

Secondary audiences create the conditions that enable wider uptake and scaling of project results. They provide the policy frameworks, knowledge platforms, and coordination mechanisms that connect local innovation with European strategies. They include:

- **European institutions and bodies** involved in climate adaptation and regional policy (e.g. DG CLIMA, DG REGIO, DG RTD, JRC, EEA, Committee of the Regions);
- **European and national policy and knowledge platforms** related to adaptation and regional development (e.g. Climate-ADAPT, Mission Implementation Platform, Smart Specialisation Platform, ESPON);

³ Deliverable D7.1 “Identifying Target Audiences”

<https://justreach.eu/sites/default/files/uploads/D7.1%20Identifying%20Target%20Audiences.pdf>

- **City and regional networks and associations** (e.g. Covenant of Mayors, ICLEI, C40, EUROCITIES, Energy Cities, Climate Alliance);
- **Research and academic organisations**, that are working on climate adaptation, just resilience and regional transformation;
- **Civil society organisations, NGOs and community organisations**, that are active in climate adaptation, environmental justice and social inclusion;
- **Private-sector actors and utilities**, that are involved in adaptation-relevant sectors such as energy, water, infrastructure, agriculture and spatial planning.

2.3 Tertiary Target Audiences

Tertiary audiences represent the wider social environment in which JustREACH operates. They are not directly responsible for implementing adaptation actions, but they influence the long-term sustainability and acceptance of adaptation policies. These are:

- **Citizens and community groups** affected by climate impacts and adaptation measures
- **Educators, schools, universities and youth networks**
- **Media actors, science communicators and opinion leaders**

The audience mapping shown in Figure 2 is treated as a living framework and will be refined as the project progresses. Updates will draw on insights from pilot activities, behavioural research, stakeholder feedback and developments in the policy and knowledge landscape. This ensures that the CDE strategy remains targeted, responsive and aligned with the evolving needs of the JustREACH adaptation ecosystem and the EU Mission on Adaptation.

Figure 2. The JustREACH ecosystem

(Source: JustREACH D7.1 Identifying Target Audiences)

3. Communication Strategy

The communication strategy of the JustREACH project sets out a coordinated and multi-channel approach to promote the project's objectives, activities and results from the start of the project. It supports visibility, understanding and engagement across a diverse range of audiences, including local and regional authorities, policymakers, practitioners and the wider public. Communication activities are designed to use appropriate tools and channels at local, regional, national and European levels, to ensure that messages are clear, targeted and relevant, and that the project's approach and contribution to just climate resilience are effectively understood.

3.1 Communication Objectives

The communication approach of JustREACH is grounded in accessible, place-based outreach that builds on the project's pilot regions as the main entry points for engagement. All communication activities are designed to ensure coherence across project outputs and channels, while remaining sensitive to local languages, institutional contexts and regional needs. It is meant to support the meaningful engagement of local communities, authorities and other stakeholders and enable participation in the development and implementation of just climate resilience approaches.

This strategy is further divided into two functional areas: **Communication on the Project** (CP) and **Communication on Content** (CC). The CP activities focus on informing stakeholders about general project developments to support the uptake of findings at both local and European levels. Meanwhile, CC activities aim to push specific facts, figures, and findings across various channels to raise awareness and trigger deeper engagement on the need for just resilience.

To ensure that the technical research translates into meaningful messages for the communities, the JustREACH communication strategy prioritises **storytelling, visual materials** and **creative campaigns** as essential tools for bridging the gap between scientific data and public motivation. Communication avoids fear-driven messaging and instead highlights practical pathways, shared responsibility and collaborative action.

In particular, the communication strategy aims to:

- **Inform** stakeholders and the wider public about the project's objectives, activities and results, and about the social and economic implications of climate change and adaptation for European regions and citizens.
- **Raise awareness** of the links between climate adaptation, social justice and regional development, and of the benefits associated with the project's approach and expected outcomes.
- **Support understanding and uptake** of project results by presenting key messages and findings in a clear, accessible and audience-specific manner.
- **Build engagement and trust** by supporting dialogue between researchers, policymakers, practitioners, communities and networks across governance levels.

3.2 Key Messages

JustREACH aligns its strategy with recent findings from the EU Mission Adaptation Community, including discussions highlighted in the 2025 Mission events,⁴ which stress the importance of moving beyond purely technical communication towards messages that are relevant, relatable and actionable for different audiences. These findings underline that effective communication on climate adaptation should focus on implementation, shared responsibility and trust, and avoid abstract concepts or risk-based narratives that can discourage engagement.

JustREACH therefore frames climate adaptation and just resilience as **practical governance challenges that require collaboration** across sectors, levels of governance and communities. Messages are tailored to specific target groups and grounded in evidence, while using clear and accessible language that connects scientific insights with real decision-making contexts. Citizen engagement and co-creation are emphasised as essential elements, recognising the role of local knowledge, lived experience and participation in shaping effective and fair adaptation pathways.

In line with Mission guidance, JustREACH communication focuses on demonstrating how adaptation measures can be implemented in practice, how they interact with social justice and regional development objectives, and how different actors can contribute to shared outcomes.

The core messages of the project are:

- **Just climate resilience is a practical governance challenge**, linked to everyday decisions, institutional capacity and implementation on the ground.
- **Climate adaptation, social justice and regional development are interconnected** and need to be addressed together to avoid unintended social and economic impacts.
- **Implementation pathways matter**, as progress is achieved through collaboration, co-creation and place-based action, rather than top-down solutions.
- **Trustworthy, accessible information supports action**, helps counter misinformation and enables informed participation by authorities, practitioners and citizens.

The tone of communication is clear, factual and inclusive, using concrete examples from pilot regions to illustrate how project results can be applied in different contexts. All messages will be refined based on insights from co-creation activities and will be adapted to specific territorial and stakeholder contexts in the future CDE updates.

3.3 Channels and Tools

JustREACH uses a range of communication channels and tools to support visibility, engagement and uptake of JustREACH results across different audiences and governance levels. These are:

3.3.1 Brand identity

A coherent visual identity has been developed to support recognition, consistency and clarity across

⁴ More on the relevant event: https://futurium.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2025-04/Summary%20report_Session%2002%202025%20event_0.pdf

all communication activities. The visual identity is applied across key materials, including the project website, social media banners, posters, leaflets and digital templates used for both online and in-person events. The project has developed a brand manual that suggests the use of Montserrat as the primary font, an open-source sans-serif typeface selected for its clarity and suitability for digital and printed materials.

Core outreach materials such as a project poster and a leaflet (Figure 3) have also been developed in English to support outreach communication at European level. These materials will be adapted and produced in local languages, to support all co-creation processes and the engagement with stakeholders in the pilot regions. Also, a set of powerpoint and word templates are available to consortium members to ensure consistency among deliverables and presentations (Figure 4).

Figure 3. Poster and flyer

Figure 4. Word and Powerpoint Templates

3.3.2 Logo

HOLISTIC, the CDE leader, developed several logo proposals for JustREACH, from which the consortium members selected the final version. The logo depicts a human figure reaching towards a leaf, symbolising the link between people and the climate. The circular form surrounding the figure represents structural and institutional limits that the project seeks to address. The logo uses a green and yellow colour palette to reflect the project’s thematic focus. Green represents climate adaptation and environmental sustainability, while yellow conveys innovation, optimism and a human-centred approach to resilience. This colour palette establishes the theme for all project-related graphics, both official documents (such as deliverables and presentation templates) and promotion materials (including visuals for social media and offline materials).

Figure 5. Logo and colour palette

3.3.3 Funding acknowledgment

All JustREACH communication, dissemination and outreach activities acknowledge European Union funding in line with European Commission requirements. Project materials display the European Union emblem together with the standard funding statement. As one project partner receives funding from the Swiss Confederation, the corresponding Swiss funding acknowledgement is also included in all relevant communication materials.

The European Union emblem appears with a minimum size of 1 cm and is placed at the bottom of the page. All references spell out “European Union” in full and do not use abbreviations. The emblem and the funding statement always appear together. Partners can access the official emblems in English and in the project partners’ languages through the shared project folder.

Figure 6. Funding Logos

All communication and dissemination materials will present factually accurate information. When materials include opinions or interpretations and display the European Union emblem, they will include the following disclaimer, translated into relevant local languages where appropriate:

“Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are, however, those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

3.3.4 Website

The JustREACH website serves as the central hub for project information and resources, providing access to the project’s objectives, activities, results, news and events. The website has been live since Month 3 and is regularly updated as the project progresses, with new sections added in response to ongoing activities. HOLISTIC developed the website and leads its maintenance and content updates throughout the project duration. In addition to the main project website, JustREACH will create dedicated landing pages in local languages for the pilot regions. These mini online hubs will host pilot-specific information, relevant project materials and invitations to events, responding to the needs of the pilot partners.

The website functions as a platform for transparency and knowledge sharing, allowing stakeholders to follow project progress, access project documentation and engage with JustREACH activities. It also acts as a repository for public deliverables, communication materials, learning resources and

dissemination outputs, ensuring that information remains organised, accessible and searchable. The project uses a web analytics service to monitor website performance and support the continuous improvement of communication and dissemination activities. The CDE leader tracks indicators such as unique, total and returning visitors, traffic sources, referrals and document downloads. Search engine optimisation (SEO) strategies are applied using specific keywords, which are reviewed and updated throughout the project lifecycle, in line with the defined key performance indicators.

Figure 7. The JustREACH Website

3.3.5 Social Media

JustREACH uses social media as a key communication tool to disseminate project activities and results, engage stakeholders and drive traffic to the project website. Social media accounts will be updated regularly with targeted content, and interaction will be encouraged. The project structures its social media presence around three main objectives:

- **informing** stakeholders through regular updates on project progress, milestones and events;
- **supporting understanding** by presenting project insights and results in accessible formats;
- **engaging** different audiences by encouraging interaction, exchange and participation.

In addition to project-managed channels, partners will support dissemination through their own institutional and professional networks, amplifying reach at local, national and European levels.

JustREACH also uses social media to engage actively within the wider adaptation and resilience ecosystem. The project team shares updates in real time during events and project activities, follows and interacts with related initiatives and Mission-relevant actors, and comments on and amplifies content from other projects and platforms. The team will also produce targeted “spill-over”

campaigns linked to pilot activities. These campaigns will highlight best practices, lessons learned and implementation experiences to support peer learning among pilot regions.

To reach different audiences effectively, JustREACH maintains project accounts on LinkedIn, Bluesky and Instagram, adapting content to the specific characteristics of each platform:

- **LinkedIn** serves as the main channel for professional communication, targeting policymakers, practitioners, researchers, networks and organisations. It shares project updates, publications, events, collaborations and links to policy-relevant outputs.
- **Bluesky** supports engagement with research, policy and expert communities through concise updates, project news and links to relevant discussions, facilitating interaction within wider adaptation and resilience networks.
- **Instagram** targets a broader audience, including citizens and local stakeholders, using visual content, short narratives and event-related material to support awareness and engagement.

A youtube account will also be created to host and publish the social learning videos, when they become available. The project uses a Linktree page to centralise access to all online resources, which can be easily shared through QR codes at events and in outreach materials (Figure 8).

Figure 8. JustREACH social media

3.3.6 Newsletter

The newsletter is a core element of the JustREACH communication strategy and supports regular information exchange with key target audiences. JustREACH produces a newsletter four times per year, using both an email-based format and a LinkedIn newsletter, to increase visibility and support engagement with project activities and results. The newsletter informs target audiences about project progress, upcoming events, key results, and synergies with other relevant initiatives. It also supports alignment with the EU Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change by sharing selected content through the Mission Adaptation Community and relevant Mission platforms, where appropriate, in line with Mission communication practices.

HOLISTIC, the CDE leader, coordinates the preparation of each issue collaboratively. A draft table of contents is shared among partners, who contribute with relevant updates from their activities. All partners actively disseminate the newsletter through their institutional channels and networks at local, national and European levels to maximise reach.

After its release, the newsletter will be uploaded to the relevant section of the JustREACH website. In compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), individuals will only be added to the newsletter mailing list with their informed and explicit consent. This consent will be collected either through an online subscription form or via direct email. Clear information on how to withdraw consent will be provided, ensuring full transparency and respect for individual privacy.

3.3.7 Press releases and blogs

Press releases and blog articles support the wider communication objectives of JustREACH as they aim to translate project activities and results into accessible narratives for wider audiences. These formats complement other communication channels by providing more contextualised and story-based content that links research, policy and practice.

Blog articles will focus on “stories from the field”, drawing on experiences from the pilot regions and project activities. These stories help bridge the gap between research and everyday realities as they present climate adaptation and just resilience through concrete examples, local perspectives and implementation experiences.

Press releases target media outlets at local, regional and European levels and communicate key project milestones, events and results. Media engagement supports wider visibility of the project and contributes to public awareness of climate adaptation challenges and solutions. Where relevant, JustREACH aligns its media outputs with EU Mission on Adaptation communication formats and storytelling approaches. An example of this approach is the Climate Story developed for Athens under the EU Mission on Adaptation,⁵ which illustrates how place-based narratives can communicate adaptation challenges and responses in an accessible and relatable way.

All partners support the identification of communication opportunities and the dissemination of press releases and blog articles through their networks, and will contribute to wider reach across

⁵ See Storytelling for encouraging climate action in Athens, Greece, https://mission-adaptation-portal.ec.europa.eu/document/download/7f018ad4-3286-411c-a4b3-00a173a03f7b_en?filename=SB_SM_Adaptation_Climate%20Story%20Athens_FINAL.pdf

regions and stakeholder groups.

3.4 Communication KPIs

This section presents the key performance indicators (KPIs) established to assess the effectiveness and reach of JustREACH's communication activities. An internal communication tracker has also been developed to constantly monitor the effectiveness of the communication activities. In Table 2, the Category column indicates whether each KPI relates to communication on the project (CP), communication on content (CC) or dissemination (D), or a combination thereof, reflecting the integrated nature of these activities in JustREACH.

Table 2. Communication KPIs

Category	Activity & Channel	Month(s)	Metrics	Monitoring tools
CP	Project Website. A centralised repository and interactive hub for results, capacity building, and local pages; includes ORCID/Zenodo integration.	6–48 (+24)	2,000 unique visitors per year	Google Analytics
CP/CC	At least 4 articles annually in newsletters of existing initiatives	3–48	1,000 total readers	Email monitoring system; Website downloads and analytics; LinkedIn newsletter subscribers
CP/CC	6 annual articles on the website and local media focusing on just climate resilience.	3–48	1,000 total readers	
CP	Social Media. Weekly posts on LinkedIn, Bluesky and Instagram to support research uptake.	3–48	>1,500 likes/shares; >700 followers per channel	Social media analytics
CC/D	2 project videos, actively promoted through all channels, using subtitles for language coverage	18, 36	500 views per video	Social media analytics
CC	Pilot specific information,	12–48	500 regular	Social media

	engagement, and “spill-over” campaigns, including in local (social) media.		viewers/readers	analytics
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4. Dissemination Strategy

The dissemination strategy of the JustREACH project aims to support the uptake of project results by local authorities, practitioners and policymakers, enable two-way knowledge exchange, and facilitate peer learning between regions. Dissemination activities build on the identification of target audiences and the development of tailored key messages that reflect their roles, needs and levels of experience. Knowledge exchange is facilitated in the project through close collaboration with the pilot regions at local, regional and European levels, which ensures that dissemination reflects place-based experiences and practical implementation challenges.

Dissemination is further supported by open access to project outputs (Figure 9), including learning materials, tools and results made available through the project website and relevant European platforms. Engagement with the target audiences and relevant stakeholders is ensured through co-creation activities, and policy-relevant events, that encourage active participation, discussion and feedback. All dissemination activities are designed to support the practical use of project results and learnings across regions.

For clarity, the CDE Plan distinguishes between platforms (technical or institutional spaces for accessing and sharing information), networks (organised groups of actors such as associations of local and regional authorities), and communities of practice (interactive spaces for peer learning and exchange), which are engaged in complementary ways throughout the project.

Figure 9. Dissemination Strategy

4.1 Dissemination Activities

Dissemination activities in JustREACH support the uptake and practical use of project results by actors involved in policy, planning and implementation. These activities build on the target audience mapping and combine participatory and peer-learning formats across local, regional, national and European levels, with a focus on place-based engagement and alignment with the EU Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change.

Across all dissemination activities, the pilot regions play a central role as sources of evidence, learning and dissemination. Pilot partners act as hubs that feed experiences, data, examples and lessons learned into the different dissemination tools and channels, including policy outreach, scientific publications, conference presentations, Mission Communities of Practice and communication materials. This approach ensures that dissemination activities remain grounded in real

implementation contexts and supports spill-over of JustREACH results to peer regions and actors beyond the pilots.

4.1.1 Workshops and co-creation events

Workshops and co-creation events are a core dissemination activity in JustREACH and are closely linked to the work carried out in the five pilot regions. The dissemination strategy supports pilot partners in **translating research findings** and project outputs on just climate resilience into workshop formats that are relevant and accessible for local and regional actors. It also **supports the promotion of these events** to ensure appropriate participation and the sharing of outcomes beyond the immediate workshop setting.

These events primarily address local and regional authority staff, pilot-site stakeholders and national or regional public agencies identified as primary audiences in Deliverable D7.1. Workshops are used to present intermediate and final project results, test tools such as the Integrated Just Resilience Framework and the JustREACH Prism and discuss implementation barriers and opportunities in real decision-making contexts. Interactive formats encourage exchange between practitioners, researchers and policymakers, helping to build a shared understanding and a sense of community around the practical challenges of implementing just climate resilience.

4.1.2 Social learning videos

Social Learning Videos are a key dissemination output of JustREACH and are co-created with actors in the pilot regions. They are primarily addressed to local and regional authorities, practitioners, community organisations and secondary and tertiary audiences such as networks, civil society organisations and media actors. The videos will document experiences from the pilot regions and show how adaptation and transformation processes unfold in practice, including the skills, conditions and trade-offs involved.

Social Learning Videos will be disseminated through the project website, partner channels and social media, and will be hosted on a dedicated YouTube channel to ensure long-term accessibility. The dissemination leader will also share the videos through EU Mission on Adaptation platforms and forums, where they will serve as a basis for discussion, exchange and peer learning around concrete challenges and solutions. In line with the proposal, a dedicated mini dissemination strategy will be developed for the Social Learning Videos once the first videos become available. This strategy will support pilot partners and the University of Bern, the lead partner for video production, in documenting the participatory video-making process and defining target audiences, key messages, formats, channels and timelines.

4.1.3 Participation in EU Mission on Adaptation Communities of Practice

JustREACH actively participates in the [EU Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change Community of Practice](#) to connect project activities with the wider Mission ecosystem and support knowledge exchange beyond the pilot regions. Participation in Mission communities ensures that discussions, lessons learned and implementation challenges emerging from JustREACH contribute to, and benefit from, collective learning across regions, cities and Mission-funded projects.

The project engages in the Mission’s Thematic Working Groups, which provide structured spaces for exchange, coordination and collaboration among Mission projects and regional actors. All relevant outputs will be submitted on the Mission Portal and the online EU Mission Adaptation Community, as part of the project’s dissemination activities. In particular, JustREACH contributes to thematic discussions relevant to its scope, including:

- **Citizen and stakeholder engagement**, which links co-creation experiences from EU-Mission regions with broader approaches to inclusive adaptation and streamlines knowledge and joint efforts for upscaling, ensuring all projects minimize duplication and increase literacy in use of climate data across European organizations.
- **Transformational adaptation**, which aims to make the concept of transformational adaptation more accessible and appealing to policymakers, regional and local governments, and potentially financial institutions and private sector actors, highlighting its relevance to the Mission Adaptation;
- **Monitoring and evaluation**, which contributes to methodologies on assessing social and economic dimensions of adaptation;
- **Climate services**, which connects JustREACH tools and frameworks with complementary initiatives on decision-support tools;
- **Financing climate action**, which aims to bridge existing funding and financing approaches, instruments, mechanisms and tools with the experience and lessons learned from Mission projects.

Figure 10. Current Thematic Working Groups under the EU Mission Adaptation Community

(Source: MIP4Adapt, April 2024)

The project consortium also engages in cross-project clustering with other EU Mission on Adaptation initiatives to increase visibility, support mutual learning, avoid duplication of efforts and strengthen the uptake and impact of project results. A non-exhaustive selection of Mission-relevant projects with which JustREACH members facilitate exchange and coordination is presented below:

- **TICCA4DANU:** This sister project supports regions and communities in the Danube area in implementing climate adaptation actions through territorial innovation and capacity building. The project focuses on translating adaptation strategies into concrete action on the ground. Exchange with TICCA4DANU supports mutual learning on place-based implementation, stakeholder engagement and the operationalisation of just and inclusive adaptation pathways, which directly aligns with JustREACH pilot activities.
- **JUST4CARE:** focuses on integrating principles of justice, equity and resilience into urban and regional climate adaptation planning. The project addresses the needs of vulnerable and marginalised groups and tests inclusive, data-driven solutions in pilot cities such as Madrid, Ankara, Budapest and Zagreb. Exchange supports reflection on equitable adaptation practices and governance approaches in urban contexts.
- **FairFuture:** addresses climate adaptation with a focus on vulnerable communities and the prevention of social inequalities. The project develops and tests inclusive adaptation measures in collaboration with local and regional authorities, national governments and community-led initiatives. Its work on resilience action labs and co-development of equitable adaptation actions provides relevant insights for JustREACH dissemination and capacity-building activities.

Additional Mission and Mission-relevant projects will be identified through the [EU Missions Project Catalogue](#) and through ongoing participation in the Mission Adaptation ecosystem, ensuring that JustREACH remains connected to emerging initiatives and collaborative opportunities.

4.1.4. Policy outreach

Policy outreach intend to support bottom-up EU policies and facilitate the potential uptake of the project's results. It will be carried out through targeted interactions with policymakers and public authorities, including bilateral meetings, when possible, participation in policy-relevant events, workshops and Mission-related fora.

Policy briefs are a key instrument supporting this outreach, translating project results into concise and accessible messages tailored to the needs of policymakers and institutional stakeholders. Policy briefs will draw in particular from project deliverables addressing adaptation pathways and assessment results, including outputs from Work Package 4 such as D4.1 Assessment of adaptation pathways and D4.2 Integrated assessment results, and translate these into policy-relevant messages for decision-makers. The briefs will be disseminated through partner networks, policy events and relevant European platforms, including those linked to the EU Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change.

4.1.5 Transformation Bootcamp

The JustREACH Transformation Bootcamp is a capacity-building activity implemented under Task T7.4 and will be organised in a later phase of the project. It targets local and regional authorities and practitioners involved in climate adaptation and regional development and builds on project results, pilot experiences and co-creation activities. The Bootcamp will support the practical application of JustREACH tools and approaches and generate learning materials that can be reused beyond the direct participants. Subsequent updates of the CDE Plan will define in more detail the concrete dissemination actions, channels and target audiences related to the Bootcamp, in line with the project's progress and available results.

4.1.6 Scientific publications

JustREACH will produce at least six open-access scientific publications between Months 12 and 48, covering the project's core scientific outputs. These include publications on the scientific principles underpinning the Integrated Just Resilience (IJR) Framework (D2.1), survey design and analysis (D3.1), agent-based models (D3.2, D3.3), the assessment model (D4.1, D4.2), co-creation processes in the pilot sites (D5.5), and the JustREACH Prism decision-support tool (D6.3, D6.4).

All publications will be made openly available and promoted through the project website, social media channels and open repositories such as Zenodo. Where relevant, simulation models will be shared through dedicated platforms such as the [COMSES](#) website to support reuse by the research community.

4.1.7 Conference presentations and side events

Conference presentations and side events support the dissemination of JustREACH results to research, policy and practitioner communities at European and international levels. JustREACH foresees participation in at least six conference presentations and special sessions between Months 12 and 48. Conference participation addresses primarily secondary and tertiary audiences identified in Deliverable D7.1, including researchers, policymakers, networks, intermediaries and practitioners, and supports dialogue on methods, tools and implementation experiences emerging from the project. Targeted events include conferences and forums such as the [Social Simulation Conference](#), the [International Association for the Study of the Commons Conference](#), [Environmental Modelling and Software](#), and the [European Geosciences Union General Assembly](#), as well as other relevant adaptation, regional development and Mission-related events. Contributions may take the form of presentations, posters, panels or organised side events, depending on the format and audience.

In addition, JustREACH will organise combined online and offline events closing the project (Task T7.5) in the final phase of implementation. These events will present key results, lessons learned and impacts to decision-makers, stakeholders and Mission actors, and will contribute to the wider dissemination and uptake of project outputs beyond the consortium.

4.2 Engagement with the wider European ecosystem

In addition to its engagement within the EU Mission on Adaptation framework, JustREACH actively connects with the wider European ecosystem of local and regional authorities, practitioner networks and policy intermediaries identified through the target audience and ecosystem mapping in Deliverable D7.1. These actors primarily correspond to secondary and tertiary target and act as multipliers for disseminating project results beyond the pilot regions. Their engagement supports the dissemination and uptake of project results beyond the Mission context and strengthens spill-over to regions, cities and organisations not directly involved in the pilot activities.

JustREACH builds on established European networks and alliances that play a key role in peer learning, capacity building and policy exchange among local and regional authorities. These include networks of cities and regions, associations of public authorities and intermediary organisations supporting climate adaptation, regional development and just transition processes, such as ICLEI and similar European and international platforms. Through these networks, project results, tools and lessons learned are shared with a broad community of practitioners and decision-makers, extending the reach of pilot-based experiences.

Engagement with the wider ecosystem complements Mission-related dissemination by leveraging communication channels, events and knowledge-sharing mechanisms already used and trusted by practitioners and policymakers. Pilot partners contribute to this engagement by mobilising their regional, national and European networks, ensuring that dissemination remains anchored in real implementation contexts while reaching audiences beyond the pilot regions. Feedback and insights gathered through engagement with the wider European ecosystem will be collected and channelled by the relevant work packages, including the development of the Integrated Just Resilience Framework and assessment outputs (WP2–WP4), the co-creation processes and Implementation Pathways in the pilot regions (WP5), and the JustREACH Prism decision-support tool (WP6), and will be taken into account in subsequent updates of the CDE Plan as results and engagement activities evolve. Engagement with the wider European ecosystem is monitored through the same indicators used for dissemination activities, including participation in events, reach through partner networks, uptake of outputs and feedback from secondary and tertiary target audiences.

4.3 KPIs

The dissemination strategy will be implemented throughout the entire lifespan of the project. An internal dissemination tracker has been developed to monitor and measure the effectiveness of the project’s dissemination activities. In Table 3, activities are labelled as Dissemination (D), Exploitation (E), or a combination of both, as several actions serve both to share project results with relevant audiences and to support their use, reuse and further development. This distinction will be further refined as the project progresses and the exploitation strategy become more clearly defined.

Table 3. Dissemination KPIs

Category	Activity and Channels	Month(s)	Metrics	Monitoring Tools
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D/ E	JustREACH Transformation Bootcamp for capacity building	30-48	50 participants in total	Lists of participants; minutes; photos
D/ E	The JustREACH Implementation Pathways	46	Participants of 5 pilot sites and then distributed to >5'000 interested citizens (>1'000 email list from each pilot partner)	Digital monitoring; website analytics and newsletter distribution
D/ E	The JustREACH Prism webtool will be available on GitHub permanently and maintained for at least 24 months after the project. Following this, the aim is to embed tool in one of the existing adaptation platforms, for example Climate ADAPT, which will be maintained over the long-term	47-48 (+24)	> 500 users of Coursera and Open edX, 311 signatories, and 500 additional regional and municipal (200 in DE, 158 in FR, remaining in HR and UK)	Digital monitoring, website analytics, GitHub unique users
D/ E	At least 6 open access scientific publications (on the scientific principles leading the IJR Framework ; on survey analysis; on the agent-based models; on the assessment model, on the co-creation processes in the pilot sites; on JustREACH Prism, widely promoted through social media, the project website and Zenodo.	12-48	550 downloads of papers (total), at least 15 uses of open data on ZENODO or equivalent, at least 100 downloads of the simulation models on COMSES	Digital monitoring, website analytics, Zenodo/GitHub unique users
D	At least 6 conference presentations and special sessions in well-selected conferences (e.g., Social Simulation	6-48	Reaching at least 2'000 participants in total	Digital monitoring, production of blogs and articles, photos

	Conference, International Associate for the study of Commons conference, Environmental modelling and software, European Geosciences Union General Assembly)			
D/ E	Combined online and offline events closing the project	43-48	850 visitors for all events and interactions	# of attendees; minutes; photos

5. Exploitation Strategy

The exploitation strategy of the JustREACH project focuses on supporting the transfer and continued use of project outputs by a diverse range of stakeholders beyond the project's official conclusion. Pilot partners play a central role in this process as they will use their established networks to share results and tailored analyses, that will help to maximise the adoption of project outputs across various sectors. To boost local transformation capacity, the project uses pilot sites as key focal points for regional impact, whereas partners integrate JustREACH outcomes into ongoing local and regional resilience missions. This influence extends indirectly through workshop participants and actors involved in case studies, who will contribute to further dissemination and uptake within their own communities.

To support these transformations, JustREACH will develop and maintain transdisciplinary learning materials tailored to various audiences. These resources, which include manuals for open data, models and software, will be hosted and regularly updated on the project website. The educational reach is further expanded through the creation of at least two online courses on platforms like Coursera, alongside intensive capacity-building events such as the Transformation Bootcamp. The project also supports implementation through accessible decision-support tools, including the IJR Checklist and the JustREACH Prism. These tools are made available through partner networks to support climate-related decision-making at local, regional and European levels.

Post-project, the website will be designed as a community of practice and handed over to THINK-E to maintain for at least 5 years following the end of the project. The hub will include access to all training materials, videos, JustREACH Prism, IJR Checklist, and other outputs from the project. Exploitation activities support the continued use, replication and further development of project results beyond the project lifetime.

The exploitation strategy of JustREACH will be further refined as the project progresses, ensuring that the roadmap for impact remains responsive to feedback from pilot regions and stakeholders. It will focus on three critical pillars: a) strengthening local capacity through pilot sites, b) providing continuous upscaling via tailored training and online courses, and c) bridging the implementation gap with new tools. This approach ensures that the project's insights will be useful and support diverse actors in advancing resilience and long-term climate action.

6. Next Steps

This first version of the CDE Plan establishes the strategic framework for communicating project activities, disseminating results and supporting their uptake and exploitation. It defines the main objectives, target audiences, tools and activities that guide CDE implementation during the initial project phases and provides a common reference for all consortium partners.

The CDE Plan is conceived as a living document and will be reviewed and updated on an annual basis to reflect project progress, feedback from pilot regions and stakeholders, and emerging dissemination and exploitation opportunities. Future updates will further specify actions, channels and target audiences as results mature and will ensure continued alignment with project deliverables, the EU Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change and the wider European ecosystem. This adaptive approach will support the coherence, relevance and impact of the CDE activities throughout the project lifetime.